

Evaluation on Optical Properties of Textile Fiber

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Abstract:

A textile fiber's optical characteristics are the actions it takes when light strikes them. Birefringence (based upon refraction of light or transmission), dichorism (based on light absorption), and lustre (based on light reflection) are some of a fiber's optical characteristics. When dyeing, printing, or matching colours on materials, optical characteristics must be taken into account. Because textile fibres were anisotropic, the direction of the fibre affects both their optical and other physical characteristics. As a result, textile fibres were birefringent (optically anisotropic), meaning that their refractive index is polarization-dependent and direction-dependent. We discuss optical properties in this article.

Keywords: Birefringence, Fibre, Light, Polarization, Refractive index, Textile

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1. Introduction

The history of textiles is almost as old with the history of human civilization, and it has become more and more enriched over time. The earliest known evidence of the use of fibre dates to the production of flax or wool fabric in an excavations of Swiss lake people in the sixth and seventh centuries BC. While cotton spinning dates back to 3000 BC, the art of silk was originally introduced to India in the year 400 AD. While the skill of spinning linen as well as weaving began to emerge in Egypt about 3400 BC, sericulture and the processes used to spin silk were first discovered in China in 2640 BC [1-3]. The industrialization of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries had a direct impact on the invention of machineries and their widespread use in processing natural fibres. As more synthetic fibres, like as nylon, were discovered, the demand for textile products grew. This eventually resulted in the development of new and improved natural fibre sources. The growth of transport and communication infrastructure paved the way for international trade in regional expertise and textile art [4-11].

The measurements corresponding to the refractive index and the birefringence offer significant information because it is understood that a lot of the structural aspects of fibres can be seen in their optical properties. A textile fiber's optical characteristics are the actions it takes when light strikes them. Birefringence (based on the refraction of light or transmission), dichorism (based on light absorption), and lustre (based on light reflection) are some of a fiber's optical characteristics [12-15].

A cloth has the ability to reflect, absorb, or transmit visible light. The degree to which light is reflected, absorbed, or transmitted determines the colour of a fabric. Thus, while dyeing, printing, or matching colours on fabrics, the optical characteristics of the fabric must be taken into account. Because textile fibres is anisotropic, the direction of the fibre affects both their optical and other physical characteristics. As a result, textile fibres become birefringent (optically anisotropic), meaning that their refractive index is polarization-dependent and direction-dependent. Therefore, we must first understand about polaization.

2. Polarisation

Confusingly, the term "polarisation" (also known as "polarisation") refers to a number of scientific phenomena, the most well-known of which may involve a selective orientation of electromagnetic waves' electric oscillations (visible light), as demonstrated by Polaroid sunglasses that use dichroism to cut down on glare. Magnetic and

electric fields the fact that oscillate in phase and at right angles to one another, as well as be perpendicular to the wave's direction of propagation, make up electromagnetic waves [16]. The Electromagnetic spectrum range is shown in figure 1 [17-20].

Figure 1: Electromagnetic Spectrum

All possible directions of vibration are equally likely, and polarisation pertains to the exact orientation of the electric field of the wave (which in turn may be orientated in only one direction as well as rotate while the wave travels). In essence, non-polarized light can be made polarised by passing through an optical filter (polarizer or polariser) that lets waves of one polarisation pass but blocks waves of other polarisations.

For instance, the filter confines the electrical vibrations to a single plane, resulting in plane-polarized light, also known as linearly polarised light, where the electric vectors were plane parallel (or plane-polarized) via relation to the direction of propagation.

The term "polarisation" refers to the propensity of a cloud of electrons inside a molecule or atom to be (temporarily) deformed by an externally applied electric field, such as that caused by an adjacent ion and dipole or, in combination of significance here, light (i.e. electromagnetic radiation). This tendency occurs in context with the optical properties of fibres. The aforementioned indicates that there are various polarisation mechanisms, including ionic polarisation (displacements among positive and negative ions in ionic crystals, such as NaCl), molecular polarisation (polar molecules within a field of electricity can experience torque that causes them to align with the applied field), and electronic polarisation (also known as electric polarisation), which is relevant to the optical properties of textile fibres. Only when light interacts with fibres do electronic operations take place since only the electrons are adequately light to react with the very high frequencies of light waves involved.

The electric field that is being applied polarises the cloud of electrons of the atoms, bonds, and molecules that make up the (transparent and translucent) fibre when light travels through it. A measure of an atom's or molecule's polarisability is the simplicity with which the existence of the electrical fields of nearby molecules can affect the arrangement of electron clouds in a non-polar species. The polarisability of the atom or molecule and the power of the electric field are connected to the induced dipole moment, which is induced by the distorted shape of the electron cloud in the initially non-polar atom or molecule. Polarisability is sometimes stated as polarisability volume, and its values frequently have magnitudes that are comparable to those of molecular volumes. Accordingly, the polarisability of electrons increasing number of electron per unit volume and is proportional to the amount of space occupied by electrons. As electronegativity rises, polarisability falls as a result of the electron clouds (or electron density's) increased confinement. This particular trait is a feature of the idea of soft and hard substances, the former of which are poorly polarisable due to their tightly confined electron clouds and have dispersed electron clouds.

Because surrounding atoms have an impact on a bond's polarisability, polarisability can be divided into three separate directions: one longitudinal direction (i.e., along the molecular and bond axis) & two transverse directions (i.e., perpendicular to a molecular and bond axis). Textile fibres have constituent molecular chains that are arranged parallel or nearly parallel to the fibre axis, yet because of the fiber's axial symmetry, both of its transverse aspects are similar

a. Polarization of Light

Unpolarized light is an electromagnetic wave. Light is spread in two different ways as it travels, including magnetic and electric fields are shown in figure 2 given below.

Figure 2: Electric and Magnetic field

Polarisation is the process through which non-polarized light is converted into polarised light. The E field of polarised light is oriented in one direction. Pictorial representation of light is shown in figure 3 [21].

Figure 3: Pictorial Representation of light

2.2 Double refraction

Certain crystals have a phenomenon called double refraction that enables them to divide an unpolarized ray to produce two plane polarised light rays at right angles to one another. The dual refraction is what causes the various colours.

2.3 O-ray & E-ray

One vibrational ray will achieve a higher refractive index during double refraction and refract in accordance with Snell's law. The Ordinary ray, often known as the O-ray, other beam that is vibrating perpendicular to the O-ray will experience a lower refractive index & will bend at a smaller angle. The E-ray, or extraordinary ray, is the name of the ray is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Double refraction. An incident ray splits into an ordinary (O) and extraordinary (E) rays

3. Refractive Index

The refractive index, also known as the index of refraction, is the ratio of the speed of light in a vacuum compared to that in the medium.

3.1 Relation among refractive index, density and swelling

The fibre density has an impact on the refraction index of the fibres. This is due to the fact that when the amount of molecules increases, the refractive index increases as well. Gladstone and Dale's law can be used to express for many fibres the correlation among refractive index and fibre density (r)

n-1

—=Constant

η

If the average reflective index is used, the value of constant is 0.3570. A similar relationship can be obtained between refractive index (n_m) and volume (v_m) of a mixture of different components [22].

3.2 Effect of moisture regain on the refractive index of fiber

Water has a refractive index of 1.33. Since most fibres have refractive index values higher than those of water, they become less transparent as moisture is regained. The influence of moisture on the mean refractive index of fibres is schematically depicted in Figure 5. When low moisture levels are restored to some fibres, a rise in the refractive index is seen, which is likely the result of water filling any holes or flaws in the fibres. [23, 24]

Figure 5: Effect of moisture regains on the refractive index of fibers

3.3 Birefringence

When a light beam strikes a fibre of textile, it divides into a pair of refracted beams, one polarised perpendicular to the fibre axis and the other parallel to the fibre axis. The birefringence value of fibre is the difference between the refractive index for light polarised parallel to the fibre axis and the refractive index for light polarised perpendicular to the fibre axis.

Figure 6: Birefringence

Birefringence can be formalized by assigning two different refractive indices to the fibre for different polarizations is shown in figure 6.

The birefringence magnitude is thus defined by-

$$\Delta n = n_1 - n_2$$

Where, for light polarised in parallel and perpendicular directions to the fibre axis, respectively, n_1 and n_2 are the refractive indices.

The highest possible level of birefringence denotes a higher degree of fibre orientation since the majority of molecules are aligned parallel with the fibre axis.

The ideal value of birefringence varies depending on how the fibres are orientated, and it ranges [25].

3.4 Factors affecting the birefringence of textile fibres:

The birefringence value of textile fibres depend on-

- the degree of orientation and
- the degree of asymmetric of the molecular chain(straight/zigzag/with side groups)

Figure 7: Fig: (a) Straight chain, (b) Zigzag chain & (c) Chain with sidegroup

The bond polarizabilities are highest along the line connecting the atoms when all of the atoms in a molecule are arranged in a straight chain as shown in figure 7 (a), which results in a high birefringence value. Although the real molecules in fibres do not take this structure, there are two reasons why their birefringence will be diminished.

First off, the majority of main chains have a zigzag shape, as seen in figure 7(b), as long as the bonds diverge from the main axis by less than around 55. This will still result in a positive birefringence value. In wool, the keratin molecule's coiling will have a similar result. Second, side groups that are attached to the primary chain, as seen in figure 7 (c), will produce atomic bonds that are perpendicular to the primary axis. In this instance, $n_{\perp}$ value reduces the Birefringence value by being higher than $n_{\parallel}$ value. In acrylic fibre, side groups have a stronger influence than the main chain, resulting in a negative Birefringence score.

3.5 Dichorism

Dichorism, which can cause differences in shadow depth or even colour itself, is the variation in radiation absorption by a coloured cloth with respect to the direction of polarisation of light.

The magnitude of it is used to gauge the positioning of molecules in dyed fibre that displays dichorism. So, we get-

$$\phi = k_1/k_2$$

Where, ϕ = Dichric/dichroitic constant

K_1 = Absorption co-efficient of light polarized parallel to the ~~h~~ axis

K_2 = Absorption co-efficient of light polarized perpendicular to the fibre axis. Lustre

A crucial characteristic of textile fibres is lustre. A light beam may reflect across an angle of reflection when it strikes a fibre surface.

The reflection may change depending on the light's colour, polarisation, and incidence angle. As regular light reflection increases, the lustre of textile fibres will consequently rise [26-30].

3.6 Requirements of Dichroism:

1. In order for the dye molecule's radiation absorption to change with the direction of the electric field activating the distinctive vibration, the dye molecule must be asymmetrical.
2. In order for all dye molecules to form the same angle with the axis of the chain molecules (or a small range of angles), the dye molecule must be absorbed onto the fibre molecule in a specific direction.
3. The molecules in the chain must be orientated preferentially.
- 4 Crossed fibres absorb more light than parallel ones: When light travels through two dichroic fibres, total absorption is higher if the fibres are crossed than if they are parallel. The explanation is rather simple: when fibres are crossed, the first fibre absorbs a significant portion of one component and the second fibre absorbs a significant portion of the opposing component. However, the same component is transmitted through both with minimal absorption if the fibres are arranged in parallel. Dichroic constant for direct dyes on cellulose: Fibre Dichroic constant Ramie 9 Viscose rayon 1.4 – 2.3 Cellophane 1.5

3.7 Reflection & Lusture

An essential aesthetic quality of fabric or textile fibre is lustre. If a light beam strikes a surface, it may reflect brilliantly at the angle of reflection as shown in figure 8 (a), diffusely with variable intensities throughout a

hemisphere as shown in figure 8 (b), or in a combination of both as shown in figure 8 (c). The reflection may change depending on the light's hue and polarisation as well as its incidence angle. The lustre of the mtl is determined by the overall visual appearance brought about by these reflections.

Figure 8: Reflection & Lustre

3.8 Factors affecting the lustre of textile fibres

Different factors affecting the lustre of different textiles are discussed below:

3.8.1 Incident angle of light

Whether the light is incident on the fibre or travels along it. A fibre would reflect light like figure 9 (a) and 9 (b) if it behaved exactly like a circular mirror. It is obvious that if light strikes the fibre, it will reflect at different angles. Instead of falling down the threads, it reflects here with a fixed angle [30, 31].

Figure 9: Incident angle of light

3.8.2 Fineness of fibre

The number of unique reflecting surfaces per unit area of a fabric increases with the number of fibres used in the fabric. The same sorts of smoothness and regularity are affected by fibre fineness, therefore the coarser fibres will have more lustre than fibre one.

3.8.3 Irregularity of the fibre surface

Light will reflect in different directions and lose its lustre as a result of irregularities on the fiber's surface and in its cross-sectional structure. It is crucial that fibres be consistent throughout their length. Because of this, the lustre is greatest in regular fibres like silk and M.M.F.

3.8.4 Fibre shape

A key element of lustre is fibre form. Due to (or as a result of) their various circular, serrated, and triangular shapes' influence on the pattern of light reflection, nylon, rayon, and silk must all have different specific forms of lustre is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Different fibre shape

3.8.5 Presentation of small particles on fibre like TiO₂ or Minimize the lustre of M.M.F

A light beam strikes a fibre and is not only reflected but also transmitted when it does so. The inside surfaces will reflect some of this transmitted light, as shown in figure 11 (a). Small particles, such as TiO₂ or cavities as shown in Figure11 (b), can scatter the transmitted light at different angles and result in a highly diffuse reflection if the fibre contains them. TiO₂ is used in MMF as a dellustrant to lessen its lustre.

Figure 11: Lustre of M.M.F

3.8.6 Maturity of fibre

A high level of maturity will also result in a high level of reflection, which will also result in a high level of lustre. Reflection Lustre of Maturity is shown in figure 12.

Figure 12: Maturity of fibre

3.8.7 Metamerism

A dye or printed fabric's colour may be noticeably altered when inspected in various lighting situations. The term "metamerism" refers to this occurrence. When viewed under one form of illumination, two fabric materials could appear to have the same colour, but when viewed underneath another type of illumination, they may appear to be an entirely different colour. The fabrics are referred to as a metameric match if this happens. When two fibres with differing chemical compositions, such polyester and cotton, must be dyed in a single colour, the issue of metameric matching may occur. The varying chemical makeup of the fibres makes it impossible to successfully colour them using the same dye in every case.

3.8.8 Delustrants

Man-made and synthetic fibres that have been extruded are frequently translucent and extremely glossy. The use of a delustrant lowers lustre and boosts opacity (and covering power). Powdered TiO₂ (particle size range: 0.3-0.4 μm in the case of PES fibres) is the most popular delustrant, while other substances like ZnS, Al₂O₃, and synthetic resins can be used as well. While additional levels of TiO₂ are used to secure fibres of different lustre, these are referred to as clear (also known as bright) in the context of fibres that do not contain delustrant, semi-matt (also known as semi-dull), and matt (also known as dull). The latter two variants are created employing additions of 0.5% as well as up to 2% TiO₂, respectively, in the case of PA fibres. Because the minute particles of usually TiO₂ in delustrant scatter the transmitted light, enhancing the quantity of diffuse reflection, the presence of delustrant throughout the fibre will lower lustre.

4. Conclusion

In this article we have discussed about the optical properties of fibre. So, as we know that the optical properties of a material define how it interact with light. Among the optical properties, refraction, absorption, reflection and scattering of light are the most important. The behavior shown by the textile fibre when light falls on it are called optical properties. A fabric can reflect, absorb or transmit visible light falling on it. The hue of the fabric depends on the extent to which light is reflected, absorbed or transmitted. Thus, optical properties of fabrics need to be taken into consideration when dyeing, printing or colour matching fabrics. Optical properties of textile fibres are birefringent in that refractive index depends on polarization of light. The refractive index of fibres is affected by fibre density. Refractive index will increase when the number of molecules present increases. For many fibres, the relationship between refractive index and fibre density is given by Gladstone and Dale's law. Besides the refractive index other factors affecting the optical properties are polarization, moisture regains, birefringence, dichroism, metamerism, and delustrants etc.

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